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Programme & the Book of Abstracts

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PROGRAMME AND THE BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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**CONFERENCE
PROGRAMME**

Monday, May 25th 2026	
8:30	Registration
9:00	Opening ceremony
SESSION 1	
	Chair: Marek Polanski
9:15	PLENARY LECTURE
	Jacques HUOT Development of High Entropy alloys for hydrogen storage
10:00	INVITED LECTURE
	Rezan DEMIR-ÇAKAN Design of Anode Materials for Practical Sodium-Ion Batteries: From Hard Carbon to Alloy Systems
10:25	Emrah DEMIR Soft-Hard Carbon Synergies for Sodium-ion Battery Anodes
10:40	Kadir TÜRKMEN (online) Tandem Copper - Cobalt Phthalocyanine Electrodes Enable Enhanced Electrochemical CO ₂ Conversion to Ethylene
10:55	Elif GÜLOĞLU (online) Comparative Electrochemical Performance Analysis of NMC Cathodes Obtained from Recovered and Commercial Materials
11:10-11:25 COFFEE BREAK	
SESSION 2	
	Chair: Fabrice Leardini
11:25	INVITED LECTURE
	Marek POLANSKI Modern Alchemy: New Strategies for the Mechanochemical Synthesis of Solid-State Hydrogen Storage Materials
11:50	Tomasz CZUJKO MgH ₂ morphological and structural changes during high-energy ball milling
12:05	Vladislav ZADOROZHNYI Effect of mechanical alloying and activation on the diffusion behavior and durability of metal hydride bulk materials
12:20	Artem KOROL (online) Comparison of residual stress values in TiFe alloy measured by sin ² Ψ and FIB-DIC techniques
12:35	David Maria TOBALDI Flexible 2D Layered Oxide Thin Films for Solid-State Hydrogen Storage

12:50 -15:00 LUNCH BREAK	
SESSION 3	Chair: Bojana Paskaš Mamula
15:00	INVITED LECTURE Nong ARTRITH (online) Harnessing Machine Learning for Advancing Amorphous Battery Materials
15:25	Katarina BATALOVIĆ From vast MXene design space to synthesizable MXENE/PANI composites: embedding guided, model driven interface engineering
15:40	Çağatay YILDIZ (online) Influence of convex enclosure structure on thermal discharge process of PCM
15:55	Branislav STANKOVIĆ Liquid-Assisted Mechanochemical Formation of CsCuCl ₃ : Insights from Machine Learning Potentials and DFT
16:10	İdil KIVANÇLI Electrochemical Noise as a Direct Probe for Copper Deposition Uniformity
Tuesday, May 26 th	
SESSION 4	Chair: Dragana Jugović
9:30	PLENARY LECTURE Vojislav STAMENKOVIĆ Progress on Electrochemical Interfaces for PEM Fuel Cells
10:15	INVITED LECTURE Fabrice LEARDINI Advanced metal chalcogenide electrocatalysts for hydrogen production by water splitting
10:40	Sevinj JAVADOVA Illumination-Dependent Electrochemical Impedance Analysis of Bi ₂ O ₃ -Based photoelectrodes
10:55	Marko JELIĆ Tailoring Surface Chemistry of Ni and Co overlayers on BiVO ₄ Thin Films for enhanced solar fuel production
11:10	Nikoloz NIORADZE Nickel doped rice husk activated carbon composites: Potential electrodes in H ₂ generation
11:25 -11:40 COFFEE BREAK	
SESSION 5	Chairs: Sanja Kurko & Tijana Pantić

11:40	INVITED LECTURE
	Eli GLIGOROVA Mg ₂ Ni based materials for hydrogen storage
12:05	Grigor TATISHVILI The importance of quantum mechanical models to explain hydrogen evolution
12:20	Gülhan ÇAKMAK Design of Composite SOFC Cathodes via Spray Pyrolysis: Synergistic Effects of Perovskite and Ruddlesden–Popper Phases
12:35	Lela KIVNIKADZE Shaping Georgia’s Green Hydrogen Transition: a Socio-Technical Triad Approach
12:50	LUNCH
20:00	CONFERENCE DINNER <i>Restaurant REKA</i>
Wednesday, May 27th	
SESSION 6	Chair: Jasmina Grbović Novaković
9:30	PLENARY LECTURE
	Mykhaylo LOTOTSKYY Features of energy storage and conversion technologies utilizing metal hydrides
10:15	INVITED LECTURE
	Fusheng YANG Recent developments on metal hydride hydrogen compressors-A comprehensive review
10:40	INVITED LECTURE
	Nikola BILIŠKOV Solid-state reactions – what we already see and what else we would like to see
11:05	Aybaniz AHADOVA (online) Isothermal decay analysis of quartz
11:25 -11:40	COFFEE BREAK
11:40	“NO DEPENDENCE” PROJECT MEETING For project participants
12:40	LUNCH BREAK
15:00	<i>Forum</i> Gender Dynamics in Science and Energy Institut francais

16:00 – 18:00	POSTER SESSION CLOSING REMARKS Institut francais
Thursday, May 28 th	
11:00	Excursion to Novi Sad Lunch and wine tasting in Winery KOVAČEVIĆ

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

P1	Nada Adamović	A1	Waste-Derived Powellite: Structural Aspects and Energy Storage Potential
P2	Ramiz Gultekin Akay	A3	Investigation of Degradation in Functionalized h-BN/PBI Composite Membranes for HT-PEMFCs
P3	Tanja Asanovic Antonic	A5	Linking Phase Stability and Oxygen-Vacancy Energetics in High-Entropy Oxide Nanofibers via Machine-Learned Potentials
P4	Gozde Atac	A6	Electrochemical Noise Analysis Coupled with EIS Interpretation in Li/MnO ₂ Primary Batteries
P5	Şebnem Cingisiz-Uygun	A9	Practical High Energy Na-Ion Batteries with Sn-Based Composite Anodes
P6	Jasmina Grbović Novaković	A11	Development of Hydrogen Compressors
P7	Jelena Jovanović	A15	Sustainable Rare Earth Recovery Using Nicotinium-based Ionic Liquid Polymer Inclusion Membranes
P8	Dragana Jugović	A16	Polymorphism and Transition Metal Doping in NaFeO ₂ -Based Cathodes
P9	Sandra Kurko	A19	MoS ₂ /Polypyrrole composites as electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Evolution Reaction
P10	Bojana Kuzmanović	A20	Synthesis and Optimization of Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x MXene Materials and Their Integration into PANI/MXene Composites
P11	Lela Kvinikadze	A21	Shaping Georgia's Green Hydrogen Transition: a Socio-Technical Triad Approach

P12	Snežana Lazić Knežević	A22	Deterministic Cost-Effective Strain Engineering of Quantum Light Emitters in Two Dimensional Semiconductors
P13	Mirjana Medić Ilić	A23	Ag and Fe Alloying in Mg ₂ Ni Systems: Impact on Surface Composition and Corrosion Behavior
P14	Sanja Milošević Govedarović	A24	Desorption kinetics from MgH ₂ -W composites
P15	Tijana Pantić	A26	X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy Study of Mg-V Thin Films for Hydrogen Storage
P16	Bojana Paskaš Mamula	A27	Computational Screening of Li and Na Amidoborane Formation
P17	Milica Prvulović	A28	Catalytic Effects of Ni and Co on MgH ₂ Hydrogen Desorption under Short Milling Times
P18	Jana Radaković	A29	Machine learning-assisted, literature-based screening of high-entropy alloys for solid state hydrogen storage
P19	Ivana Radisavljević	A30	Effects of 3d metal doping on local and electronic structure of CeO ₂ nanopowders
P20	Zilong Wang	A36	Optimal control on a single stage metal hydride hydrogen compressor: A Pontryagin minimization approach
P21	Aygün Zeynalova	A41	The influence of the composition of Ni-P thin films on their electrocatalytic properties
P22	Šaban Žuna	A42	The Role of Hydrogen in the HDH Process for Producing Titanium Alloy Powder for Additive Manufacturing

PLENARY LECTURES

Isothermal decay analysis of quartz

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The analysis of isothermal decay in thermoluminescence (TL) provides critical insights into the trapping and recombination mechanisms governing luminescence in materials. In first-order kinetics, charge carriers are released from traps without significant retrapping, resulting in a simple exponential decay. However, real-world systems often exhibit deviations from idealized behavior due to competing pathways, retrapping effects, or higher-order kinetics. The linear relationship between $\ln(I)$ and time in first-order kinetics facilitates straightforward determination of activation energy (E), making it a cornerstone of TL analysis. The inclusion of general-order kinetics expands the applicability of these studies by accommodating complex TL behaviors, particularly in fields such as dosimetry and geochronology, where precise trap characterization is vital for accurate dose reconstruction and age determination. By analyzing decay curves at varying temperatures, the resulting slope differences $\ln(I)$ versus time plots offer insights into the underlying kinetic processes.

Figure 1. Plot of the natural logarithm of TL intensity versus time at different T_{stop} temperature. T_{stop} temperatures are indicated in the legend

Figure 1 illustrates the time-dependent TL intensity decay at constant temperature for quartz samples preheated at 500 °C on a semi-log scale. Subsequently, samples were heated to a predefined T_{stop} temperature, followed by TL signal recording under isothermal conditions (100 s stabilization). For TL peaks governed by first-order kinetics, isothermal decay follows an exponential trend, as described in. A linear dependency of $\ln(\text{TL intensity})$ versus time plot confirms first-

order behavior, with the slope yielding $-E/kT$ and the intercept corresponding to $\ln(s/\beta)$. Nonlinearity in such plots, however, indicates deviations from first-order kinetics. The plots generated from the data in Fig. 1 demonstrated nonlinearity, indicating that the TL data does not conform to first-order kinetics. The general-order kinetics equation suggests that plotting $(I_t / I_0)^{(1-b)/b}$ as a function of time should result in a straight-line relationship when an appropriate kinetic order parameter (b) is selected according to [2]:

$$\left(\frac{I(t)}{I_0}\right)^{\frac{(1-b)}{b}} = 1 + (b-1)\frac{t}{\tau} \neq 1$$

where $I(t)$ is the intensity of the luminescence signal as a function of time; τ is the lifetime for isothermal decay; and b is the order of kinetics.

However, when the general-order kinetics approach was applied to the isothermal decay data in Fig. 1 using kinetic order parameters $b=1.9, 2.0, 2.1$, and 2.2 , none of the tested values produced a statistically valid linear fit. This outcome highlights a fundamental challenge in analyzing isothermal decay data, as subtle graphical variations for different b values complicate the identification of an optimal kinetic order. The persistent lack of linearity across all tested b values strongly suggests that the TL decay does not conform to second-order kinetics. This conclusion was further reinforced by repeating the analysis on additional datasets in Fig. 1, all of which similarly failed to align with second order kinetic behavior.

To explore alternative explanations for the observed decay dynamics, the superposition of two or three exponential functions—each linked to distinct trapping centers—was evaluated [1]:

$$I_t = I_{01} \exp(-P_1 t) + I_{02} \exp(-P_2 t) + \dots$$

where I_{0n} is the phosphorescence intensity due to electrons in the traps of energy E_n , $P_n = s \exp(-E_n/kT)$ is the probability of an electron escaping from a trap, k is the Boltzmann constant, and s is the escape frequency factor. A detailed decomposition of the decay curves into such components was attempted to resolve individual activation energies (E). However, the results revealed that the decay profiles cannot be accurately modeled as a sum of two or three first-order exponential terms, ruling out a simple superposition of first-order processes.

Subsequent efforts to deconvolute the curves using second order kinetic components also proved unsuccessful, further underscoring the complexity of the underlying trapping-

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recombination mechanisms. Intriguingly, the isothermal decay data were best described by combining two single exponential decay terms with a constant offset, a phenomenon previously reported in studies of natural quartz. For instance, successfully modeled similar isothermal decay profiles using three exponential components and a constant term.

Collectively, the nonlinearity observed in Fig. 1 and analogous datasets in the literature implies that the TL signal arises from contributions of multiple trapping centers. The relative influence of these centers appears temperature dependent, leading to deviations from idealized exponential decay behavior. This complexity challenges conventional

kinetic models and underscores the need for advanced analytical frameworks to account for heterogeneous trap distributions and dynamic recombination pathways.

Acknowledgment

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- [2] Furetta, C. et al. *Appl. Radiat. Isot.*, 69, 346–349 (2011)

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